

Neo-Charismatic Movement - Third Wave Charismatic Movement

By Nathan Womack, University of California, Riverside

Entry tags: Evangelical Religion, Religious Group, Protestantism

Pentecostal and Charismatic practices of speaking in tongues through the Baptism of the Holy Spirit had become accepted within many mainline Protestant denominations and the Roman Catholic Church by the 1960s and 1970s. However, many evangelical traditions and churches continued to resist charismatic renewal practices and theologies during the rise of the Second Wave Charismatic Renewal Movement. Charismatics were viewed with suspicion and their practices were critiqued and mocked within evangelical circles. Yet, evangelicalism was not immune to change during the 1960s and 1970s. The hippie-led Jesus People Movement took hold in the United States during this time. Young barefoot preachers would encourage their peers to turn away from drugs, accept Jesus Christ as their Lord and Savior, and join a new type of church that emphasized a come-as-you-are vibe with casual dress and provided rock and roll as part of their worship liturgy. In addition, many of the new hippie converts were interested in Charismatic practices of healing and witnessing through signs and wonders. The Jesus People Movement led to the formation of new independent evangelical churches that identified as non-denominational and some of these churches embraced Charismatic theology and practices. One of the church movements that emerged in the late 1970s was the Vineyard Church in Southern California. The Vineyard was a collection of churches that broke away from Calvary Chapel due to the Vineyard's desire to emphasize Charismatic practices and theology. On Mother's Day in 1980, Pastor John Wimber of the Vineyard Christian Fellowship in Orange County, CA and invited a former Calvary Chapel pastor and the face of the Jesus People Movement, Lonnie Frisbee, to preach. Frisbee's message on healing and the subsequent ministry of healing that took place that morning launched the start of the Vineyard Movement and subsequent Neo-Charismatic movement. This new Neo-Charismatic movement blended evangelical theology with charismatic practices of healing, supernatural prayer languages, and an emphasis on miraculous signs and wonders as a component of evangelism. John Wimber began to teach at Fuller Theological Seminary in Pasadena, CA and was influenced by C. Peter Wagner's research on church growth as well as George Ladd's Kingdom of God theology. Wimber was able to influence numerous people to start their own independent charismatic churches and ministries as a faculty member and through his conferences that he hosted where he taught on how to minister using supernatural signs and wonder. Wimber developed the concept of "power evangelism" where adherents evangelized using signs and wonders rather than Bible tracts that were popular in the 1960s and 1970s. By the 1990s, new independent churches and movements that were evangelical and charismatic were rapidly emerging throughout North America. These included the Toronto Blessing Movement began in 1994 at the Toronto Airport Vineyard Church. Bethel Church in Redding, CA installed Pastor Bill Johnson as their senior pastor in 1996. The International House of Prayer Kansas City was founded in 1999. These Neo-Charismatic churches and others have become popular and controversial for their encouragement of the miraculous, their non-formal style of liturgy, and theological stances on healing, anointing, and supernatural power. C. Peter Wagner coined the term "Third Wave" charismatic movement to describe these new churches and ministries. Their emphasis on power evangelism, charismatic forms of worship, healing, prayer languages, operating in signs and wonders, and their emphasis on anointing leaders as apostles and prophets made them distinct from traditional Pentecostal churches and Charismatic Renewalists within mainline traditions.

Date Range: 1980 CE - 2020 CE

Region: USA

Region tags: North America, United States of America, United States, Lower 48

The United States of America

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: C. Peter Wagner. *The Third Wave of the Holy Spirit: Encountering the Power of Signs and Wonders Today*. Servant Publications, Vine Books, 1988.
- Source 1: Vinson Synan. *The Century of the Holy Spirit: 100 Years of Pentecostal and Charismatic Renewal*. Thomas Nelson Publishers: Nashville, TN, 2001.
- Source 1: Bill Johnson. *When Heaven Invades Earth*. Treasure House: Shippensburg, 2003.
- Source 2: John Wimber. *Power Evangelism*. Regal: Ventura, 1985.
- Source 3: Kris Vallotton. *Spirit Wars*. Chosen Books: Bloomington, 2012.
- Source 1: Che Ahn. *Modern-Day Apostles: Operating in Your Apostolic Office and Anointing*. Destiny Image Books, 2019.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=U6TDE41wdEc>
- Source 1 Description: Bill Johnson from Bethel Church in Redding, CA teaching on healing.
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wGkobOn363A&list=PLAm1XlvCYgMLC8Af2Y7PYn1GQXsR6cuyp>
- Source 1 Description: John Wimber's Signs and Wonders Conference in 1985.
- Source 1 URL: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4h_KsyYaB4E
- Source 1 Description: International House of Prayer - 24 hour livestream of prayer and worship
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0PFShMsp9bM>
- Source 1 Description: Che Ahn from Harvest Rock Church in Pasadena, CA teaches on lifestyle evangelism
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2ylugDXtStw>
- Source 1 Description: Lonnie Frisbee gives a sermon on Mother's Day in 1980 at Yorba Linda Vineyard, a church pastored by John Wimber. John Wimber and Lonnie Frisbee are two of the pioneers of the Third Wave Neo-Charismatic Movement.
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IIT3oaaed9U>
- Source 1 Description: This video is of a sermon during the Toronto Blessing movement that began in 1994. This movement began in a Vineyard Church at the Toronto Airport Christian Fellowship and evolved into

its own stream of Neo-Charismatic churches and networks.

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics use the Protestant Bible that contains the 39 books of the Old Testament and 27 books of the New Testament. Neo-Charismatics believe that the Bible is divinely inspired and is infallible in regards to its teachings.

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

Are they written:

– Yes

Are they oral:

– No

Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: Some parts of the Bible, such as the Ten Commandments, were revealed directly by God. Other parts of the Bible were inspired by God rather than revealed.

Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe the Bible to be "God-breathed" as stated in 1 Timothy 3:16-17. They believe the Bible to have ultimate authority because it was God authored.

Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

Notes: The scriptures that contain the teachings of Jesus Christ originate from a divine-human being since Neo-Charismatics adhere to the evangelical theology of hypostasis where Jesus Christ is fully God and fully man.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics adhere to a spectrum of views regarding the origins of the Biblical texts but many hold to a position of plenary-verbal inspiration. This means that the human authors had agency in writing the texts but God provided the inspiration to write them.

Reference: Gorman, Michael J.. Elements of Biblical Exegesis. Baker Books, 2008.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=Z4oUe60jHm0C>.

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The Neo-Charismatic movement has its roots in evangelicalism in the United States. The movement comes into contact with different evangelical denominations and non-denominational churches. Many charismatic churches that identify as or can trace their roots to the genesis of the movement self-identify as non-denominational churches.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: There is cultural competition between Neo-Charismatics and non-charismatic evangelicals. Pastors such as John MacArthur in Los Angeles, CA have hosted conferences and taught sermons denouncing the Neo-Charismatic movement. You can view teachings from the Strange Fire Conference in 2013 at <https://www.gty.org/library/topical-series-library/325/strange-fire-conference> as well as read a transcript from one of MacArthur's sermons that outlines his problems with any form of Charismatic Renewal traditions, including the Neo-Charismatic Movement, here: <https://www.gty.org/library/sermons-library/TM13-18/an-appeal-to-charismatic-friends-john-macarthur> Other evangelicals have taken issue with the use of Neo-Charismatic music and worship styles. Opponents of charismatic songs and worship styles contend that the theological statements in the songs are not biblical. Check out this video of an interview that outlines the issues that some evangelicals have with music from Bethel and Hillsong: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Y0uFSYHVSrk> One group of churches in particular transitioned from being part of the neo-charismatic movement to being traditionally evangelical. Calvary Chapel is a group of churches (they are not an official denomination although they are often categorized as one by practitioners and outside observers) that was started by Pastor Chuck Smith in the 1960s and rose to prominence during the Jesus Movement during the late 1960s and 1970s. Pastor Chuck was a pastor within the Foursquare denomination but left to start a non-denominational church during the 1960s. During the Jesus Movement, Chuck Smith met a young hippie named Lonnie Frisbee, on the beaches in Orange County. Frisbee accepted Jesus Christ as his savior and he became one of Chuck Smith's pastors at Calvary Chapel Costa Mesa. Frisbee drew in thousands of the hippie youth to Smith's church and Frisbee taught on the Baptism of the Holy Spirit and encouraged others to practice their spiritual gifts. During the

1970s, Smith started to de-emphasize the Baptism of the Holy Spirit and he and Frisbee parted ways due to the theological stances Calvary Chapel took regarding the movement of the Holy Spirit. Calvary Chapel's emphasis was on literal Bible teachings and by the 1980s became known for their preaching approach going verse by verse of each book of the Bible. Many Calvary Chapels still believe in the modern-day practice of the gifts of the Holy Spirit but they do not emphasize them and Calvary Chapel has distanced themselves from their history with Lonnie Frisbee.

Reference: Eskridge, Larry. *God's Forever Family*. USA: Oxford University Press, 2013.
https://books.google.com/books/about/God_s_Forever_Family.html?hl=&id=kW2qKgZrte4C.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: The Neo-Charismatic Movement is pluralistic in some respects in regards to accepting many evangelical, Pentecostal, and other Protestant theologies and doctrines. However, the movement is not accomodating with other aspects of culture such as open and pluralistic stances regarding sexual and gender identity.

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 48459000

Reference: Johnson, Todd M.. "The Global Demographics of the Pentecostal and Charismatic Renewal". *Society* 46, no. 6 (November 1, 2009): 479–83. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12115-009-9255-0>.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: The Neo-Charismatic movement is not a centralized movement and thus does not have a

governing body to monitor or approve who is a Neo-Charismatic and who is not. However, self-identification is the primary way that congregations identify as Charismatic. Often, they put their Charismatic identification in their statement of faith.

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Those who identify as Charismatic within the Neo-Charismatic movement do so by personal choice.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Like Pentecostals and Charismatics, Neo-Charismatics believe that a believer ought to be baptized in the Holy Spirit. This event is often, but not always, subsequent to conversion where a person accepts Jesus Christ as their Lord and Savior. A believer must earnestly seek the Baptism of the Holy Spirit and often receives prayer and guidance from another person as they attempt to receive the baptism. The difference between Neo-Charismatics and Pentecostals is proof of evidence that a person has been baptized in the Holy Spirit. Pentecostals believe that a person must speak in tongues when they are baptized in the Holy Spirit. Charismatics and Neo-Charismatics believe that any manifestation of the gifts of the Holy Spirit is evidence that the person has been baptized.

Reference: Synan, Vinson. *The Century of the Holy Spirit*. Nashville, TN: Thomas Nelson, 2000.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 15.7

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: The Neo-Charismatic movement emerged out of evangelicalism in the United States. Evangelizing is a common practice amongst Neo-Charismatics and they not only share the gospel but they demonstrate the gospel through signs and wonders such as prophetic words, words of knowledge, healings, and other miracles. Here is a video of Pastor and Evangelist Todd White ministering to Satanists in Brazil in 2019.

Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatic clergy have a biblical mandate from Jesus Christ to go and make disciples all over the world. They are trained in evangelism to go and share the gospel with others.

Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

Notes: Adherents are not mandated to do anything but they are highly encouraged to be witnesses to the world and share the gospel with everyone.

Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: The Neo-Charismatic Movement has iconography centered on the concept of prophetic art. Many adherents believe that God speaks to people through art and the Holy Spirit often gives them visions and pictures of what to paint, draw, sculpt, or design. Some Neo-Charismatic churches have ministries

devoted to the creation of prophetic art - <https://bethelredding.com/content/creative-arts>

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- On persons
- At home
- Only religious public space

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Much of the prophetic art that is created and used during worship services depict Jesus Christ as a lion or the Holy Spirit as a dove.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

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↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There are people who have left Neo-Charismatic churches and who have renounced their identification with the movement. Their renunciation is self-imposed and there is no formal label that is put on them by others since there is no centralized Neo-Charismatic leadership or body.

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Many Neo-Charismatic churches arrange tours to Israel for their congregations. They spend time touring holy sites and holding worship services throughout different places on their tour.

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (rare)

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

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Size and Structure

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Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

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↳ Are they written:

– Yes

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<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=Z4oUe60jHm0C>.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

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↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

- Yes

↳ Humans:

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↳ Other features of iconography:

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Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

- No

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Many Neo-Charismatic churches arrange tours to Israel for their congregations. They spend time touring holy sites and holding worship services throughout different places on their tour.

How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (rare)

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that humans are made of mind, body, and spirit. They believe that a person's spirit lives beyond physical death and that a person will be reunited with their body through resurrection during the end times.

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.

<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that God desires for people to follow him and to live their lives in such a way that brings glory to God and brings life and purpose to them. God knows how people act and live. However, there is a semantic distinction regarding how God deals with actions that are not in line with his person and the Bible. Kris Vallotton, a pastor at Bethel Church in Redding, CA explains, "The devil often finds an open door to condemn us when we do something wrong. The Lord convicts us when we sin. The difference between condemnation and conviction may seem subtle, but it can be deadly.

Condemnation says, 'You lied, therefore you are a liar. You got drunk, therefore you must be an alcoholic.' Condemnation tries to convince us that our bad action is the fruit of being a bad person. On the other hand, conviction says, 'You are way too awesome to act like that.' Conviction reminds us of our God-given identity and calls us to act like a son or daughter of God, not a sinner." There is an emphasis on identity as it relates with spiritual monitoring within Neo-Charismatic teachings. Neo-Charismatics shift the conversation away from condemnation and shame and move it toward a re-orientation of how a believer ought to see themselves as being in the image of God and the power that they possess as image-bearers. This does not mean that there are no consequences for actions that violate God's word and desires. Yet, the emphasis is on helping people understand their value and worth in God's eyes is not dependent on what they do or do not do. Rather, their value is intrinsic to their identity as image-bearers of God.

Reference: Vallotton, Kris. *Spirit Wars*. Baker Books, 2012. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=SWZIs9KGsicC>.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

— Yes

Notes: God desires for people to honor oaths and care for those in need. Ministries such as Youth With A Mission's mercy ships provide practical medical care around the world. Benevolence ministries are rooted in Neo-Charismatic theology of demonstrating the love of God through both practical care and signs and wonders.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

— No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

— Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe the Bible teaches against murder in any form. This belief is consistent with other Christian traditions who point to the Ten Commandments, Jesus Christ's teaching on murder, and other texts in the Bible that condemn murder in any form.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

— Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

— Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

— Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics are conservative in terms of their views on LGBTQ identity. They believe that God designed sex for married men and women for the purposes of enjoyment and pro-

creation.

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that God forbids adultery in the Bible. They base their claim on biblical passages from both the Old and New Testaments.

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Homosexuality

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that God designed sexual intercourse to be between a married man and a woman. There are ministries that offer counseling and resources to individuals who want to leave their LGBTQ lifestyle. In 2019, Neo-Charismatic ministries led the way to oppose a proposed California legislative bill that would have outlawed pastors and churches from counseling individuals who wanted to no longer identify as LGBTQ. See the organization Equipped to Love for more information: <https://www.equippedtolove.com/>

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that lying violates God's Word in the Bible. Lying, amongst other things, positions people to allow demonic influences to shape their thinking and actions.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: God is opposed to sorcery and witchcraft. Many Neo-Charismatics believe that people who are spiritually oppressed by demons need deliverance. Some of those who need deliverance needs to be delivered from the practice of sorcery. Hear a deliverance prayer from sorcery and witchcraft from Robert Clancy: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OF3HsCl_jWo

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: Rituals and liturgy are fluid within many Neo-Charismatic communities. They are often Spirit-led meaning that the leader is responsible for adjusting a worship service or prayer gathering according to the leading of the Holy Spirit. The proper ritual and liturgical observance is found in the fluidity of the moment rather than strict ritual observance.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that all followers of Jesus Christ must be baptized in water as an outward sign of their conversion. They also believe that all Christians ought to partake in communion or the Eucharist. There is not an emphasis on a proper way these rituals are conducted but the emphasis is on the heart behind the actions of the ritual. Listen to a sermon from Pastor Bill Johnson on the purpose of communion: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gh9hvXgSqCU>

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics are grounded in evangelical theology and practice. They believe that it is necessary to evangelize and make new disciples of Jesus Christ. Neo-Charismatics emphasize that sharing the gospel with others means allowing the Holy Spirit to give insight and wisdom about a person's life and for the believer to speak into that revelation in order to share the good news of the gospel. See Pastor John Wimber's teaching on evangelizing in power: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4yeezMyR_xU

Reference: Wimber, John, and Kevin Springer. *Power Evangelism*. Gospel Light Publications, 2009. https://books.google.com/books/about/Power_Evangelism.html?hl=&id=xbaHaraYZMIC.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics encourage adherents to live in such a way that positions them to be used by God to expand his kingdom. Social norms such as financial and material generosity, sexual purity, monogamy, and hospitality are not just practices that make God happy; they are an important part of being in relationship with God where God can use them to bless others and demonstrate his love for all people.

Reference: Ahn, Ché. *God Wants to Bless You!*. Chosen Books, 2015.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=jpgQBgAAQBAJ>.

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that Jesus Christ is the Messiah or Anointed One who fulfills God's plan of redemption for all creation. The death and resurrection of Jesus Christ allow all people to have a relationship with God. While many other Christian traditions and even some Charismatic traditions emphasize Jesus Christ's messianic Second Coming, Neo-Charismatics put a large emphasis on Jesus Christ's messianic role in the present in addition to his second coming. Pastor Bill Johnson from Bethel Church in Redding, CA explains, "The resurrection power of God is available for every situation." Jesus Christ's resurrection power is bestowed upon believers who have been Baptized in the Spirit and who desire to minister as Jesus did. See the short clip from a teaching about resurrection power:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=p790ahQrGAA>

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that Jesus Christ will return as a king who will fully usher in the Kingdom of God. The Book of Revelation gives depictions of Jesus Christ as a king with a crown, sword, and a throne.

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that Jesus Christ is the ultimate priest as identified in Hebrews 4:14-16. Jesus Christ is the ultimate mediator and intercessor between people and the Father.

↳ Other purpose:

– No

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe in supernatural beings that are good and evil. There is a belief amongst Neo-Charismatics that followers of Jesus are mandated to practice spiritual warfare. Spiritual warfare is the practice of fighting against supernatural forces of evil that desire to thwart God's mission. Peter Wagner and the Lausanne Covenant explains, "We believe that we are engaged in constant spiritual warfare with the principalities and powers of evil, who are seeking to overthrow the Church and frustrate its task of world evangelization. We know our need to equip ourselves with God's armour and to fight this battle with the spiritual weapons of truth and prayer. For we detect the activity of our enemy, not only in false ideologies outside the Church, but also inside it in false gospels which twist Scripture and put people in the place of God. We need both watchfulness and discernment to safeguard the biblical gospel."

Reference: Wagner, C. Peter. *Spiritual Warfare Strategy*. Destiny Image Publishers, 2011.
https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=K-Ch6w_9uT4C.

Reference: First Lausanne Congress. "The Lausanne Covenant". The Lausanne Movement, n.d..
<https://www.lausanne.org/content/covenant/lausanne-covenant#cov>.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe in trinitarian monotheism. They believe that there is one God who is three co-eternal substances: The Father, Son, and Holy Spirit. Their theological position on the Trinity is consistent with other evangelicals. However, Neo-Charismatics place a greater emphasis on the person and work of the Holy Spirit compared to other Christian traditions.

Reference: Wagner, C. Peter. *The Third Wave of the Holy Spirit*. Servant Publications, 1988.
https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Third_Wave_of_the_Holy_Spirit.html?hl=&id=E6jxPAAACAAJ.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: God is spoken about with anthropomorphic terms such as face or hands. It is common to hear Neo-Charismatics talk about the face of God or being touched by the hand of God.

- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes

Notes: God is believed to be unquestionably good, even in the midst of chaos and evil. Neo-Charismatics point to Biblical passages such as Exodus 34:6 and Psalm 100:5 that declare God's goodness. See teaching on the goodness of God by Graham Cooke - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=djT70GgzhWw>

- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Yes [specify]: God is a healer

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe God to be a healer who wants to heal people physically and emotionally. Adherents ought to seek God's healing in their lives as well as the lives of others. It is common for Neo-Charismatic pastors and leaders to teach about healing. Here is a short teaching from Randy Clark about how to pray for healing: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xisjm2Mbzes>

Reference: Wimber, John, and Kevin Springer. *Power Healing*. Harper Collins, 1991. https://books.google.com/books/about/Power_Healing.html?hl=&id=Hbni8yprTYwC.

- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of

human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that God knows the hearts and minds of all people. Neo-Charismatics point to Biblical passages such as Jeremiah 17:10 where God declares that he knows the hearts and minds of people. Neo-Charismatic pastors often teach about the importance of the purity of the heart and mind. See Bill Johnson's sermon: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=R5QaifMPDsc>

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe in the sovereignty of God and they believe that God has a plan for humanity. However, many Neo-Charismatics do not hold to

the Calvinist position that many Reformed traditions hold to regarding predestination and salvation. Neo-Charismatics tend to be more Arminian in their theology. Yet, Neo-Charismatics believe that God knows who will and will not be healed. God's will is to heal everyone but not everyone will experience healing prior to the Second Coming of Jesus Christ when Heaven and Earth will be renewed. See Bill Johnson's teaching on the will of God and healing: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3p-n47dVtQ8>

Reference: Johnson, Bill, and Randy Clark. *Healing Unplugged*. Baker Books, 2012. https://books.google.com/books/about/Healing_Unplugged.html?hl=&id=jJFvZKB6qXcC.

Reference: Johnson, Bill, and Randy Clark. *The Essential Guide to Healing*. Baker Books, 2011. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=ktageZChnQcC>.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
– No

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:
– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that God can and does reward those who are faithful. The rewards can be tangible and material things such as money or health. However, many Neo-Charismatics believe that rewards are experienced in the form of miracles. These supernatural phenomena have been described as seeing gold dust or diamonds appearing during a worship service. Watch this video from Bethel Church in Redding, CA to see a "glory cloud" appear during a service: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lvJMPccZR2Y>

↳ The supreme high god can punish:
– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that God can punish and will administer justice and judgment in the last days. However, many Neo-Charismatics emphasize that God is loving and good and although he can punish people, he usually withholds any sort of punishment or wrath until the end of time.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– No

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: God is seen in the Old Testament exhibiting negative emotion. Jesus Christ also exhibits negative emotion in the New Testament. Neo-Charismatics teach about grieving the Holy Spirit and how the Holy Spirit can be grieved by believers.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics emphasize the need to hear God's voice. Followers of Jesus need to spend time reading the Bible, praying, and meditating in order to hear the Holy Spirit speak. God not only can speak to people but also desires to speak to them in order to build them up and empower them for the ministry he has called them to. See an interview with Bill Johnson on hearing God's voice: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Mjc91eGjzZw>

Reference: Jacobs, Cindy. *The Voice of God*. Chosen Books, 2016. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=bTqRDQAAQBAJ>.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that God communicates to people through dreams. See a teaching from Benny Hinn on how God speaks through dreams: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WBFS5xxa8Q8>

Reference: Vallotton, Kris. "4 Keys for Understanding Your Dreams". www.krisvallotton.com, March 29, 2019. <https://www.krisvallotton.com/4-keys-for-understanding-your-dreams/>.

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: Neo-Charismatics emphasize that God speaks to all people and not just clergy. Followers of Jesus are encouraged to learn how to converse with God. See a sermon from Joyce Meyer on how to speak with God:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=b5ea0P2xSR8>

Reference: Meyer, Joyce. How to Hear from God. FaithWords, 2004.

<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=iROjqori2MoC>.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that humans are able to yield "territory" to demons. Territory refers to any physical spaces or mental and emotional spaces

within a person. Demons are able to gain an understanding of particular domains of human affairs as humans relinquish them. See a teaching from Bill Johnson: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uibD1cNoK4Y>

Reference: Vallotton, Kris. *Spirit Wars*. Baker Books, 2012.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=SWZIs9KGsicC>.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: Demons are able to see inside the hearts and minds of people as people allow them to. Neo-Charismatics teach that believers must engage in spiritual warfare to combat demonic influence. See a teaching from Che Ahn on *Confronting the Powers of Darkness*: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SUI7WpaL8BA>

Reference: Meyer, Joyce. *Battlefield of the Mind*. FaithWords, 2008.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=8kl2TDV9kmoC>.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that angels rejoice when sinners repent and get saved by accepting Jesus Christ as their Lord and Savior. They base their belief on Luke 15:10 that says, "In the same way, I tell you, there is rejoicing in the presence of the angels of God over one sinner who repents."

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe in a variety of spiritual beings including angels, cherubim, seraphim, demons, and Satan.

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that there is a hierarchy amongst angels and that there are archangels who have particular roles to fulfill compared with other angels and heavenly beings. See Bill Johnson's teaching on angels: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1uJ0gochpaM>

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe in a literal Heaven and Hell and many Neo-Charismatic pastors teach about Heaven and Hell in their sermons. However, teachings about Heaven are rooted in Kingdom of God theology and many Neo-Charismatics believe that Jesus did not preach a gospel about going to Heaven or avoiding Hell but rather preached about living in and for the Kingdom of God. Neo-Charismatics believe that there is an overlap between Heaven and earth through the life, death, and resurrection of Jesus Christ. They believe that people can experience Heaven on earth to some degree and that followers of Jesus ought to bring Heaven to earth through miracles, healings, prophetic words, and loving others. See Bill Johnson teach on bringing Heaven to earth: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_85bCON5YhU

Reference: Ladd, George Eldon, and Donald Alfred Hagner. *A Theology of the New Testament*. Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing, 1993. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=eldkMOOEdIAC>.

Reference: Vallotton, Kris. *How Heaven Invades Earth*. Gospel Light Publications, 2013.

https://books.google.com/books/about/How_Heaven_Invades_Earth.html?hl=&id=LsFAhYPIX7wC.

Reference: Johnson, Bill. *When Heaven Invades Earth*. Destiny Image Publishers, 2016.

https://books.google.com/books/about/When_Heaven_Invades_Earth.html?hl=&id=E2zxDwAAQBAJ.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: Heaven and Hell are literal spaces beyond the present world. See Todd White's interview answer questions about Heaven and Hell: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vMw_SD6Aj6w

Reference: Vallotton, Kris. *How Heaven Invades Earth*. Gospel Light Publications, 2013.
https://books.google.com/books/about/How_Heaven_Invades_Earth.html?hl=&id=LsFAhYPIX7wC.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics embrace many conservative social norms within their churches. However, there is a casual atmosphere for church services, prayer gatherings, and conferences. The casual atmosphere can be traced to the Jesus People Movement that began in California in the late 1960s that consisted primarily of hippies from the counter-cultural movement. Since the Neo-Charismatic movement emerged from the Second Wave Charismatic Renewal and evangelicalism, it follows that the Neo-Charismatics would follow their causal traditions in terms of dress and worship style of folk and rock music. Neo-Charismatics have also embraced contemporary artistic expressions through prophetic art and dance. These types of expressions may not be embraced by mainline Charismatic traditions or other evangelical groups. See an explanation of prophetic art - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YwXsNIbaKMc> See the dress and style of worship at a Neo-Charismatic worship service - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UGFCbmvk0vo>

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present (but not emphasized)

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatic churches and ministries encourage their congregants to adhere to specific moral norms that are often outlined in a covenant document. These documents are commonly available on the church's website and are often distributed during membership classes held by the church. In addition to agreeing with the theology of the church, the covenants also outline moral norms such as avoiding intoxication through drugs and alcohol, sexual purity, monogamy, and regular financial contributions through tithes and offerings. See Bethel Church's covenant here: <https://bethelredding.com/membership#qt-membership-ui-tabs2>

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics follow the teachings of Jesus Christ and interpret them as a typology of how to live in both Heaven and earth in the present day. The moral norms that Jesus Christ taught are not just good ideas. They are the way that adherents can position themselves to receive more power and authority to minister to others and make more disciples for the Kingdom of God. See Kris Vallotton's teaching called Living from Eternity - <https://www.krisvallotton.com/living-from-eternity>

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

- All individuals within society
- All individuals within contemporary world
- All individuals (any time period)

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Eschatologically, God will mete out punishment for those who reject him. God will judge the world and make all things right. Neo-Charismatics emphasize that God does not condemn those who are Christ Jesus. See Todd White's teaching on condemnation: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KNiaZmFjS5o>

Reference: Ladd, George Eldon, and Donald Alfred Hagner. *A Theology of the New Testament*. Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing, 1993. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=eIdkM00EdIAC>.

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: God's judgment and resulting punishment are based upon people choosing to reject God. There is a belief in a literal Lake of Fire amongst Neo-Charismatics and that space is for people who chose to accept God's grace and the gift of salvation. See Todd White's response on Heaven and Hell: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vMw_SD6Aj6w

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Many Neo-Charismatics emphasize a literal Hell and that people who reject the gift of salvation in this lifetime are permanently separated from God for eternity. However, Neo-Charismatics avoid teaching fire and brimstone type messages. Rather, they emphasize God's love and his desire for all humanity to be redeemed and restored in relationship with God.

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe in a resurrection from the dead for all people but not reincarnation. This is consistent with other beliefs about the resurrection from other Christian traditions.

Reference: Livingston, James C.. *Anatomy of the Sacred*. Prentice Hall, 2008.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Anatomy_of_the_Sacred.html?hl=&id=5pCNHwAACAAJ.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics teach about God's desire to bless his people. God blesses those who trust him and follow him. Neo-Charismatics teach that God's blessings are for the present age and for eternity.

Many preachers also teach that God has promises for people and that God will fulfill those promises in people's lives through perseverance and faith. See Pastor Kris Vallotton teach on promises:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EjbFN4lhaEU>

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics teach similar eschatological concepts as evangelicals about the end times and afterlife in eternity. They hold to a literal reading of the Book of Revelation where believers will live with God for eternity and there will be no more pain, tears, suffering, or death.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The emphasis is not on rewards but rather is on the concept of blessings. God

desires to bless people in many ways whether it is through personal fulfillment, purpose, or through physical well-being and healing.

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– No

Notes: Many Neo-Charismatics believe that God will politically bless those who implement conservative and biblical standards in civic government. There is also a belief that all leaders are appointed by God. Many Neo-Charismatic pastors teach about the importance of followers of Jesus being in positions of political authority and power in order that a nation continues to be blessed by God. See Pastor Che Ahn's teaching about the Spiritual Fight for America: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=i3bU7QcsiuY>

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

Notes: Many Neo-Charismatics pray a prayer of traveling mercies. These prayers focus on God blessing the travelers and that he would protect them and guide them.

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Notes: Part of God's blessing on earth is found in Genesis 1:28 where God charges humans to be fruitful and multiply. Many Neo-Charismatics pray for God to open up the wombs of barren women and that God would bless children and families.

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics emphasize generational blessings. God not only desires to bless people today but those blessings carry over into future generations. See Marilyn Hickey's teaching on generational blessings: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-cd_sq553cE

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: One practice that takes place in cemeteries is called grave sucking or grave soaking. Some Neo-Charismatic adherents believe that apostolic and prophetic leaders leave behind their anointing when they die. That anointing can be transmitted by laying their hands on or prostrating oneself on the gravesite of the deceased leader. The basis for this practice is found in 2 Kings 13:21 that says, "Once while some Israelites were burying a man, suddenly they saw a band of raiders; so they threw the man's body into Elisha's tomb. When the body touched Elisha's bones, the man came to life and stood up on his feet." This practice is controversial amongst Neo-Charismatics and some pastors and preachers teach against the practice. Many fundamentalist and evangelical opponents of the Neo-Charismatic movement decry these practices as unbiblical. See a response from Pastor Bill Johnson from Bethel Church in Redding,

CA to grave soaking - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uCes2PZVFC4> See a practitioner explain grave soaking - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LrHPTs8cLLs>

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

Notes: Many Neo-Charismatic churches embrace inner healing and they encourage their adherents to speak up when they are struggling with a particular issue. Adherents are also encouraged to "be above reproach" meaning that they are to go above and beyond in terms of their integrity and honesty, even if it is not expected in a particular situation.

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatic emphasis on healing encourages adherents to be compassionate and benevolent towards others. See Bill Johnson's teaching on compassion - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1meGN4IQd-o>

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

— Yes

Notes: Forgiveness and mercy are core aspects of Neo-Charismatic practice and theology. Jesus Christ's work on the cross and his resurrection brought about forgiveness of sins for the whole world. Neo-Charismatics are encouraged to forgive others just as Jesus Christ did in the first century. See Dan Mohler's teaching on mercy - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=O1iQLe_FLWs

↳ Generosity / charity:

— Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics have similar views as other evangelical groups in regards to generosity and stewardship. God gives people material goods and money to bless others. Followers of Jesus must steward their finances well in order to position themselves to bless others who need assistance. Neo-Charismatics expand on the theology of stewardship by articulating beliefs that blessings from generosity extend into the supernatural realm. See Kris Vallotton's teachings on generosity - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=a5IFCkzhIk8>

Reference: Vallotton, Kris. *Poverty, Riches and Wealth*. Chosen Books, 2018. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=mwNJDwAAQBAJ>.

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

— Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

— Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

— Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics emphasize the concept of spiritual strongholds that can keep people in demonic bondage. These strongholds can be accessed through everyday activities such as watching movies that depict evil and witchcraft to playing video games that emphasize violence and death. Neo-Charismatics are encouraged to abstain from activities that could allow demonic entities to influence their lives. See Bill Johnson's teaching on the work of the Devil - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QAf4qBHN4Ds>

Reference: Liebscher, Teresa, and Dawna De Silva. *SOZO Saved Healed Delivered*. Destiny Image Publishers, 2016. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=LfTPDAAAQBAJ>.

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

— Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

— Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics encourage creativity in their ministries. Adherents are encouraged to find their passions and use them to fuel their passion for evangelism and healing.

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics are encouraged to be bold with their faith and to trust God to use them to bring healing to others. Many pastors teach on the importance of being bold in their faith and asserting their faith in God. See Bill Johnson's teaching on boldness -

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=R-xn-JefX5I>

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics teach that power and status must be reframed around the supernatural. They teach that governments in the world are set up by God and that they are to be honored as long as they are operating out of the principles of the Bible. Neo-Charismatics also teach that each follower of Jesus Christ is anointed with power and status and nobility as children of God. They believe that all Christians ought to embrace their birthright as God's children and exercise their authority over demonic authorities. See Dan Mohler's teaching on authority - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=H5bM_52XVBw

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics encourage people to experience the joy of the Lord and live joyful lives. Their worship songs can reflect this idea. See a worship song that contains lyrics on joy as well as spontaneous bouts of laughter - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jCRfqCNWoHs>

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics encourage adherents to be in awe of God's person and his presence as well as what he has done in their lives. Many worship services spend time reflecting on God's person and character.

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

Notes: Faith is a crucial component of Neo-Charismatic culture. Pastors teach their congregants about the necessity of faith and how to use their faith to minister to others. See Bill Johnson's teaching on faith - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xWbLA3Er_kU

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

Notes: A popular spiritual gift that is used by Neo-Charismatics is the gift of discernment. Adherents are encouraged to seek out the discernment of the Holy Spirit before making decisions and when engaging with other people.

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– No

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that humans are made of mind, body, and spirit. They believe that a person's spirit lives beyond physical death and that a person will be reunited with their body through resurrection during the end times.

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe in a literal Heaven and Hell and many Neo-Charismatic pastors teach about Heaven and Hell in their sermons. However, teachings about Heaven are

rooted in Kingdom of God theology and many Neo-Charismatics believe that Jesus did not preach a gospel about going to Heaven or avoiding Hell but rather preached about living in and for the Kingdom of God. Neo-Charismatics believe that there is an overlap between Heaven and earth through the life, death, and resurrection of Jesus Christ. They believe that people can experience Heaven on earth to some degree and that followers of Jesus ought to bring Heaven to earth through miracles, healings, prophetic words, and loving others. See Bill Johnson teach on bringing Heaven to earth: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_85bCON5YhU

Reference: Ladd, George Eldon, and Donald Alfred Hagner. *A Theology of the New Testament*. Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing, 1993. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=eIdkM00EdIAC>.

Reference: Vallotton, Kris. *How Heaven Invades Earth*. Gospel Light Publications, 2013. https://books.google.com/books/about/How_Heaven_Invades_Earth.html?hl=&id=LsFAhYPIX7wC.

Reference: Johnson, Bill. *When Heaven Invades Earth*. Destiny Image Publishers, 2016. https://books.google.com/books/about/When_Heaven_Invades_Earth.html?hl=&id=E2zxDwAAQBAJ.

Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: Heaven and Hell are literal spaces beyond the present world. See Todd White's interview answer questions about Heaven and Hell: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vMw_SD6Aj6w

Reference: Vallotton, Kris. *How Heaven Invades Earth*. Gospel Light Publications, 2013. https://books.google.com/books/about/How_Heaven_Invades_Earth.html?hl=&id=LsFAhYPIX7wC.

Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– No

Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe in a resurrection from the dead for all people but not reincarnation. This is consistent with other beliefs about the resurrection from other Christian traditions.

Reference: Livingston, James C.. *Anatomy of the Sacred*. Prentice Hall, 2008. https://books.google.com/books/about/Anatomy_of_the_Sacred.html?hl=&id=5pCNHwAACAAJ.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: One practice that takes place in cemeteries is called grave sucking or grave soaking. Some Neo-Charismatic adherents believe that apostolic and prophetic leaders leave behind their anointing when they die. That anointing can be transmitted by laying their hands on or prostrating oneself on the gravesite of the deceased leader. The basis for this practice is found in 2 Kings 13:21 that says, "Once while some Israelites were burying a man, suddenly they saw a band of raiders; so they threw the man's body into Elisha's tomb. When the body touched Elisha's bones, the man came to life and stood up on his feet." This practice is controversial amongst Neo-Charismatics and some pastors and preachers teach against the practice. Many fundamentalist and evangelical opponents of the Neo-Charismatic movement decry these practices as unbiblical. See a response from Pastor Bill Johnson from Bethel Church in Redding, CA to grave soaking - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uCes2PZVFC4> See a practitioner explain grave soaking - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LrHPTs8cLLs>

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe in supernatural beings that are good and evil. There is a belief amongst Neo-Charismatics that followers of Jesus are mandated to practice spiritual warfare. Spiritual warfare is the practice of fighting against supernatural forces of evil that desire to thwart God's mission. Peter Wagner and the Lausanne Covenant explains, "We believe that we are engaged in constant spiritual warfare with the principalities and powers of evil, who are seeking to overthrow the Church and frustrate its task of world evangelization. We know our need to equip ourselves with God's armour and to fight this battle with the spiritual weapons of truth and prayer. For we detect the activity of our enemy, not only in false ideologies outside the Church, but also inside it in false gospels which twist Scripture and put people in the place of God. We need both watchfulness and discernment to safeguard the biblical gospel."

Reference: Wagner, C. Peter. *Spiritual Warfare Strategy*. Destiny Image Publishers, 2011.
https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=K-Ch6w_9uT4C.

Reference: First Lausanne Congregess. "The Lausanne Covenant". The Lausanne Movement, n.d..
<https://www.lausanne.org/content/covenant/lausanne-covenant#cov>.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe in trinitarian monotheism. They believe that there is one God who is three co-eternal substances: The Father, Son, and Holy Spirit. Their theological position on the Trinity is consistent with other evangelicals. However, Neo-Charismatics place a greater emphasis on the person and work of the Holy Spirit compared to other Christian traditions.

Reference: Wagner, C. Peter. *The Third Wave of the Holy Spirit*. Servant Publications, 1988.
https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Third_Wave_of_the_Holy_Spirit.html?hl=&id=E6jxPAAACAAJ.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: God is spoken about with anthropomorphic terms such as face or hands. It is common to hear Neo-Charismatics talk about the face of God or being touched by the hand of God.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: God is believed to be unquestionably good, even in the midst of chaos and evil. Neo-Charismatics point to Biblical passages such as Exodus 34:6 and Psalm 100:5 that declare God's goodness. See teaching on the goodness of God by Graham Cooke - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=djT70GgzHwW>

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: God is a healer

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe God to be a healer who wants to heal people physically and emotionally. Adherents ought to seek God's healing in their lives as well as the lives of others. It is common for Neo-Charismatic pastors and leaders to teach about healing. Here is a short teaching from Randy Clark about how to pray for healing: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xisjm2Mbzes>

Reference: Wimber, John, and Kevin Springer. *Power Healing*. Harper Collins, 1991. https://books.google.com/books/about/Power_Healing.html?hl=&id=Hbni8yprTYwC.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that God knows the hearts and minds of all people. Neo-Charismatics point to Biblical passages such as Jeremiah 17:10 where God declares that he knows the hearts and minds of people. Neo-Charismatic pastors often teach about the importance of the purity of the heart and mind. See Bill Johnson's sermon: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=R5QaifMPDsc>

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe in the sovereignty of God and they believe that God has a plan for humanity. However, many Neo-Charismatics do not hold to the Calvinist position that many Reformed traditions hold to regarding predestination and salvation. Neo-Charismatics tend to be more Arminian in their theology. Yet, Neo-Charismatics believe that God knows who will and will not be healed. God's will is to heal everyone but not everyone will experience healing prior to the Second Coming of Jesus Christ when Heaven and Earth will be renewed. See Bill Johnson's teaching on the will of God and healing: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3p-n47dVtQ8>

Reference: Johnson, Bill, and Randy Clark. *Healing Unplugged*. Baker Books,

2012. https://books.google.com/books/about/Healing_Unplugged.html?hl=&id=jJFvZKB6qXcC.

Reference: Johnson, Bill, and Randy Clark. *The Essential Guide to Healing*. Baker Books, 2011. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=ktageZChnQcC>.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
– No

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:
– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that God can and does reward those who are faithful. The rewards can be tangible and material things such as money or health. However, many Neo-Charismatics believe that rewards are experienced in the form of miracles. These supernatural phenomena have been described as seeing gold dust or diamonds appearing during a worship service. Watch this video from Bethel Church in Redding, CA to see a "glory cloud" appear during a service: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lvJMPccZR2Y>

↳ The supreme high god can punish:
– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that God can punish and will administer justice and judgment in the last days. However, many Neo-Charismatics emphasize that God is loving and good and although he can punish people, he usually withholds any sort of punishment or wrath until the end of time.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– No

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– Yes

Notes: God is seen in the Old Testament exhibiting negative emotion. Jesus Christ also exhibits negative emotion in the New Testament. Neo-Charismatics teach about grieving the Holy Spirit and how the Holy Spirit can be grieved by believers.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics emphasize the need to hear God's voice. Followers of Jesus need to spend time reading the Bible, praying, and meditating in order to hear the Holy Spirit speak. God not only can speak to people but also desires to speak to them in order to build them up and empower them for the ministry he has called them to. See an interview with Bill Johnson on hearing God's voice:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Mjc91eGjzZw>

Reference: Jacobs, Cindy. *The Voice of God*. Chosen Books, 2016.

<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=bTqRDQAAQBAJ>

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that God communicates to people through dreams. See a teaching from Benny Hinn on how God speaks through dreams:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WBFS5xxa8Q8>

Reference: Vallotton, Kris. "4 Keys for Understanding Your Dreams".

www.krisvallotton.com, March 29, 2019. <https://www.krisvallotton.com/4-keys-for-understanding-your-dreams/>.

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: Neo-Charismatics emphasize that God speaks to all people and not just clergy. Followers of Jesus are encouraged to learn how to converse with God.

See a sermon from Joyce Meyer on how to speak with God:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=b5ea0P2xSR8>

Reference: Meyer, Joyce. *How to Hear from God*. FaithWords, 2004.

<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=iROjqori2MoC>.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that humans are able to yield "territory" to demons. Territory refers to any physical spaces or mental and emotional spaces within a person. Demons are able to gain an understanding of particular domains of human affairs as humans relinquish them. See a teaching from Bill Johnson: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uibD1cNoK4Y>

Reference: Vallotton, Kris. *Spirit Wars*. Baker Books, 2012.

<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=SWZIs9KGsicC>.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: Demons are able to see inside the hearts and minds of people as people allow them to. Neo-Charismatics teach that believers must engage in spiritual warfare to combat demonic influence. See a teaching from Che Ahn on Confronting the Powers of Darkness: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SUI7WpaL8BA>

Reference: Meyer, Joyce. *Battlefield of the Mind*. FaithWords, 2008. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=8kl2TDV9kmoC>.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that angels rejoice when sinners repent and get saved by accepting Jesus Christ as their Lord and Savior. They base their belief on Luke 15:10 that says, "In the same way, I tell you, there is rejoicing in the presence of the angels of God over one sinner who repents."

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe in a variety of spiritual beings including angels, cherubim, seraphim, demons, and Satan.

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.

<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that there is a hierarchy amongst angels and that there are archangels who have particular roles to fulfill compared with other angels and heavenly beings. See Bill Johnson's teaching on angels:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1uJ0gochpaM>

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that God desires for people to follow him and to live their lives in such a way that brings glory to God and brings life and purpose to them. God knows how people act and live. However, there is a semantic distinction regarding how God deals with actions that are not in line with his person and the Bible. Kris Vallotton, a pastor at Bethel Church in Redding, CA explains, "The devil often finds an open door to condemn us when we do something wrong. The Lord convicts us when we sin. The difference between condemnation and conviction may seem subtle, but it can be deadly. Condemnation says, 'You lied, therefore you are a liar. You got drunk, therefore you must be an alcoholic.' Condemnation tries to convince us that our bad action is the fruit of being a bad person. On the other hand, conviction says, 'You are way too awesome to act like that.' Conviction reminds us of our God-given identity and calls us to act like a son or daughter of God, not a sinner." There is an emphasis on identity as it relates with spiritual monitoring within Neo-Charismatic teachings. Neo-Charismatics shift the conversation away from condemnation and shame and move it toward a re-orientation of how a believer ought to see themselves as being in the image of God and the power that they possess as image-bearers. This does not mean that there are no consequences for actions that violate God's word and desires. Yet, the emphasis is on helping people understand their value and worth in God's eyes is not dependent on what they do or do not do. Rather, their value is intrinsic to their identity as image-bearers of God.

Reference: Vallotton, Kris. *Spirit Wars*. Baker Books, 2012. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=SWZIs9KGsicc>.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: God desires for people to honor oaths and care for those in need. Ministries such as Youth With A Mission's mercy ships provide practical medical care around the world. Benevolence ministries are rooted in Neo-Charismatic theology of demonstrating the love of God through both practical care and signs and wonders.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe the Bible teaches against murder in any form. This belief is consistent with other Christian traditions who point to the Ten Commandments, Jesus Christ's teaching on murder, and other texts in the Bible that condemn murder in any form.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics are conservative in terms of their views on LGBTQ identity. They believe that God designed sex for married men and women for the purposes of enjoyment and pro-creation.

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that God forbids adultery in the Bible. They base their claim on biblical passages from both the Old and New Testaments.

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

–Yes [specify]: Homosexuality

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that God designed sexual intercourse to be between a married man and a woman. There are ministries that offer counseling and resources to individuals who want to leave their LGBTQ lifestyle. In 2019, Neo-Charismatic ministries led the way to oppose a proposed California legislative bill that would have outlawed pastors and churches from counseling individuals who wanted to no longer identify as LGBTQ. See the organization Equipped to Love for more information: <https://www.equippedtolove.com/>

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that lying violates God's Word in the Bible. Lying, amongst other things, positions people to allow demonic influences to shape their thinking and actions.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: God is opposed to sorcery and witchcraft. Many Neo-Charismatics believe that people who are spiritually oppressed by demons need deliverance. Some of those who need deliverance needs to be delivered from the practice of sorcery. Hear a deliverance prayer from sorcery and witchcraft from Robert Clancy: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OF3HsCl_jWo

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: Rituals and liturgy are fluid within many Neo-Charismatic communities. They are often Spirit-led meaning that the leader is responsible for adjusting a worship service or prayer gathering according to the leading of the Holy Spirit. The proper ritual and liturgical observance is found in the fluidity of the moment rather than strict ritual observance.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that all followers of Jesus Christ must be baptized in water as an outward sign of their conversion. They also believe that all Christians ought to partake in communion or the Eucharist. There is not an emphasis on a proper way these rituals are conducted but the emphasis is on the heart behind the actions of the ritual. Listen to a sermon from Pastor Bill Johnson on the purpose of communion: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gh9hvXgSqCU>

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics are grounded in evangelical theology and practice. They believe that it is necessary to evangelize and make new disciples of Jesus Christ. Neo-Charismatics emphasize that sharing the gospel with others means allowing the Holy Spirit to give insight and wisdom about a person's life and for the believer to speak into that revelation in order to share the good news of the gospel. See Pastor John Wimber's teaching on evangelizing in power: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4yeezMyR_xU

Reference: Wimber, John, and Kevin Springer. *Power Evangelism*. Gospel Light Publications, 2009. https://books.google.com/books/about/Power_Evangelism.html?hl=&id=xbaHaraYZMIC.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Eschatologically, God will mete out punishment for those who reject him. God will judge the world and make all things right. Neo-Charismatics emphasize that God does not condemn those who are Christ Jesus. See Todd White's teaching on condemnation: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KNiaZmFjS5o>

Reference: Ladd, George Eldon, and Donald Alfred Hagner. *A Theology of the New Testament*. Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing, 1993. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=eldkM00EdIAC>.

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: God's judgment and resulting punishment are based upon people choosing to reject God. There is a belief in a literal Lake of Fire amongst Neo-Charismatics and that space is for people who chose to accept God's grace and the gift of salvation. See Todd White's response on Heaven and Hell: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vMw_SD6Aj6w

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Many Neo-Charismatics emphasize a literal Hell and that people who reject the gift of salvation in this lifetime are permanently separated from God for eternity. However, Neo-Charismatics avoid teaching fire and brimstone type messages. Rather, they emphasize God's love and his desire for all humanity to be redeemed and restored in relationship with God.

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics teach about God's desire to bless his people. God blesses those who trust him and follow him. Neo-Charismatics teach that God's blessings are for the present age and for eternity. Many preachers also teach that God has promises for people and that God will fulfill those promises in people's lives through perseverance and faith. See Pastor Kris Vallotton teach on promises: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EjbFN4lhaEU>

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics teach similar eschatological concepts as evangelicals about the end times and afterlife in eternity. They hold to a literal reading of the Book of Revelation where believers will live with God for eternity and there will be no more pain, tears, suffering, or death.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The emphasis is not on rewards but rather is on the concept of blessings. God desires to bless people in many ways whether it is through personal fulfillment, purpose, or through physical well-being and healing.

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– No

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
– No
Notes: Many Neo-Charismatics believe that God will politically bless those who implement conservative and biblical standards in civic government. There is also a belief that all leaders are appointed by God. Many Neo-Charismatic pastors teach about the importance of followers of Jesus being in positions of political authority and power in order that a nation continues to be blessed by God. See Pastor Che Ahn's teaching about the Spiritual Fight for America: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=i3bU7QcsiuY>
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
– No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
– No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
– No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
– Yes
Notes: Many Neo-Charismatics pray a prayer of traveling mercies. These prayers focus on God blessing the travelers and that he would protect them and guide them.
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
– No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
– No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
– Yes
Notes: Part of God's blessing on earth is found in Genesis 1:28 where God charges humans to be fruitful and multiply. Many Neo-Charismatics pray for God to open up the wombs of barren women and that God would bless children and families.
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics emphasize generational blessings. God not only desires to bless people today but those blessings carry over into future generations. See Marilyn Hickey's teaching on generational blessings: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-cd_sq553cE

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that Jesus Christ is the Messiah or Anointed One who fulfills God's plan of redemption for all creation. The death and resurrection of Jesus Christ allow all people to have a relationship with God. While many other Christian traditions and even some Charismatic traditions emphasize Jesus Christ's messianic Second Coming, Neo-Charismatics put a large emphasis on Jesus Christ's messianic role in the present in addition to his second coming. Pastor Bill Johnson from Bethel Church in Redding, CA explains, "The resurrection power of God is available for every situation." Jesus Christ's resurrection power is bestowed upon believers who have been Baptized in the Spirit and who desire to minister as Jesus did. See the short clip from a teaching about resurrection power: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=p790ahQrGAA>

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that Jesus Christ will return as a king who will fully usher in the Kingdom of God. The Book of Revelation gives depictions of Jesus Christ as a king with a crown, sword, and a throne.

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that Jesus Christ is the ultimate priest as identified in Hebrews 4:14-16. Jesus Christ is the ultimate mediator and intercessor between people and the Father.

↳ Other purpose:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics encourage adherents to live in such a way that positions them to be used by God to expand his kingdom. Social norms such as financial and material generosity, sexual purity, monogamy, and hospitality are not just practices that make God happy; they are an important part of being in relationship with God where God can use them to bless others and demonstrate his love for all people.

Reference: Ahn, Ché. *God Wants to Bless You!*. Chosen Books, 2015.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=jpgQBgAAQBAJ>.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics embrace many conservative social norms within their churches. However, there is a casual atmosphere for church services, prayer gatherings, and conferences. The casual atmosphere can be traced to the Jesus People Movement that began in California in the late 1960s that consisted primarily of hippies from the counter-cultural movement. Since the Neo-Charismatic movement emerged from the Second Wave Charismatic Renewal and evangelicalism, it follows that the Neo-Charismatics would follow their causal traditions in terms of dress and worship style of folk and rock music. Neo-Charismatics have also embraced contemporary artistic expressions through prophetic art and dance. These types of expressions may not be embraced by mainline Charismatic traditions or other evangelical groups. See an explanation of prophetic art - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YwXsNlbaKMc> See the dress and style of worship at a Neo-Charismatic worship service - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UGFCbmvkOvo>

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present (but not emphasized)

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatic churches and ministries encourage their congregants to adhere to specific moral norms that are often outlined in a covenant document. These documents are commonly available on the church's website and are often distributed during membership classes held by the church. In addition to agreeing with the theology of the church, the covenants also outline moral norms such as avoiding intoxication through drugs and alcohol, sexual purity, monogamy, and regular financial contributions through tithes and offerings. See

Bethel Church's covenant here: <https://bethelredding.com/membership#qt-membership-ui-tabs2>

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:
– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics follow the teachings of Jesus Christ and interpret them as a typology of how to live in both Heaven and earth in the present day. The moral norms that Jesus Christ taught are not just good ideas. They are the way that adherents can position themselves to receive more power and authority to minister to others and make more disciples for the Kingdom of God. See Kris Vallotton's teaching called Living from Eternity - <https://www.krisvallotton.com/living-from-eternity>

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:
– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:
– All individuals within society
– All individuals within contemporary world
– All individuals (any time period)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:
– Yes

Notes: Many Neo-Charismatic churches embrace inner healing and they encourage their

adherents to speak up when they are struggling with a particular issue. Adherents are also encouraged to "be above reproach" meaning that they are to go above and beyond in terms of their integrity and honesty, even if it is not expected in a particular situation.

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatic emphasis on healing encourages adherents to be compassionate and benevolent towards others. See Bill Johnson's teaching on compassion - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1meGN4lQd-o>

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

Notes: Forgiveness and mercy are core aspects of Neo-Charismatic practice and theology. Jesus Christ's work on the cross and his resurrection brought about forgiveness of sins for the whole world. Neo-Charismatics are encouraged to forgive others just as Jesus Christ did in the first century. See Dan Mohler's teaching on mercy - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=O1iQLe_FLWs

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics have similar views as other evangelical groups in regards to generosity and stewardship. God gives people material goods and money to bless others. Followers of Jesus must steward their finances well in order to position themselves to bless others who need assistance. Neo-Charismatics expand on the theology of stewardship by articulating beliefs that blessings from generosity extend into the supernatural realm. See Kris Vallotton's teachings on generosity - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=a5lFCkzhIk8>

Reference: Vallotton, Kris. *Poverty, Riches and Wealth*. Chosen Books, 2018. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=mwNJDwAAQBAJ>.

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics emphasize the concept of spiritual strongholds that can keep people in demonic bondage. These strongholds can be accessed through everyday activities such as watching movies that depict evil and witchcraft to playing video games that emphasize violence and death. Neo-Charismatics are encouraged to abstain from activities that could allow demonic entities to influence their lives. See Bill Johnson's teaching on the work of the Devil - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QAf4qBHN4Ds>

Reference: Liebscher, Teresa, and Dawna De Silva. *SOZO Saved Healed Delivered*. Destiny Image Publishers, 2016. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=LfTPDAAAQBAJ>.

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics encourage creativity in their ministries. Adherents are encouraged to find their passions and use them to fuel their passion for evangelism and healing.

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics are encouraged to be bold with their faith and to trust God to use them to bring healing to others. Many pastors teach on the importance of being bold in their faith and asserting their faith in God. See Bill Johnson's teaching on boldness - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=R-xn-JefX5I>

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics teach that power and status must be reframed around the supernatural. They teach that governments in the world are set up by God and that they are to be honored as long as they are operating out of the principles of the Bible. Neo-Charismatics also teach that each follower of Jesus Christ is anointed with power and status and nobility as children of God. They believe that all Christians ought to embrace their birthright as God's children and exercise their authority over demonic authorities. See Dan Mohler's teaching on authority - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=H5bM_52XVBw

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics encourage people to experience the joy of the Lord and live joyful lives. Their worship songs can reflect this idea. See a worship song that contains lyrics on joy as well as spontaneous bouts of laughter - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jCRfqCNWoHs>

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics encourage adherents to be in awe of God's person and his presence

as well as what he has done in their lives. Many worship services spend time reflecting on God's person and character.

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

Notes: Faith is a crucial component of Neo-Charismatic culture. Pastors teach their congregants about the necessity of faith and how to use their faith to minister to others. See Bill Johnson's teaching on faith - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xWbLA3Er_kU

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

Notes: A popular spiritual gift that is used by Neo-Charismatics is the gift of discernment. Adherents are encouraged to seek out the discernment of the Holy Spirit before making decisions and when engaging with other people.

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– No

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that men should not have sexual intercourse until they are

married. They encourage adherents to practice abstinence until marriage. Men are to be the husband of one wife.

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that women should not have sexual intercourse until they are married. They encourage adherents to practice abstinence until marriage. Women are to be the wife of one husband.

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Men are not to engage in sexual intercourse with other men. Homosexuality is believed to be in violation of God's original design for marriage and sex.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Women are not to engage in sexual intercourse with other women. Homosexuality is believed to be in violation of God's original design for marriage and sex.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: Fasting is not required amongst Neo-Charismatics but it is highly encouraged. Many adherents believe that fasting ought to be part of their lifestyle and many preachers teach on the importance of fasting and how the practice positions believers to hear from the Holy Spirit. See Todd White's teaching on a lifestyle of fasting: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=clr3uJl6Jic>

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Like other Christian traditions and denominations, Neo-Charismatics believe that it is important for followers of Jesus Christ to regularly meet for worship, prayer, and teaching. Many Neo-Charismatic churches have services devoted to extended times of prayer and worship. There are also ministries that are devoted to 24-hour prayer and worship such as the International House of Prayer in Kansas City, MO. See the website for the International House of Prayer Kansas City (IHOPKC) to view a 24-hour webstream of worship and prayer: <https://www.ihopkc.org/>

Reference: Bickle, Mike. *Growing in Prayer*. Charisma Media, 2014.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Growing_in_Prayer.html?hl=&id=11dTBAQAQBAJ.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that the Bible contains God's Word and that it outlines ethical precepts that need to be followed in order to further God's Kingdom and allow the Holy Spirit to transform a believer's life. Neo-Charismatics take conservative stances on abortion and LGBTQ issues and offer resources to their members in regard to these positions. Churches like Bethel Church in Redding, CA have websites to further their ethical precepts: <https://bethelredding.com/unplanned>

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Membership Costs and Practices

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Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

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– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics have built their own schools that teach students the methods and doctrines of supernatural ministry. Churches such as Bethel Church founded Bethel School of Supernatural Ministry in Redding, CA. Other schools such as Wagner University have branched off from their home church (Harvest Rock in Pasadena, CA) and have become stand alone institutes that train men and women to minister out of the power of the Holy Spirit. See Wagner University at <https://wagner.university/> and Bethel School of Supernatural Ministry at <https://bssm.net/>

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Do the group’s adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that there are Biblical offices and positions within the church that have greater authority than others. Many Neo-Charismatics believe that there are some leaders who are called as apostles or prophets in the modern-day. The emphasis on the role and function of apostles is not about organizational bureaucracy but rather is focused on personal leadership. Che Ahn explains, “Notice what apostolic government is shifting away from - bureaucratic authority, legal structure, control, and

rational leadership. Notice what apostolic government is shifting to - personal authority, relational structure, coordination, and charismatic leadership. For apostolic government to be effective, it must rely on the personal leadership of apostles rather than organizational systems."

Reference: Ahn, Ché. *Modern-day Apostles*. Destiny Image Publishers, 2019.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=IW2ADwAAQBAJ>.

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: Tithing is a common practice amongst Neo-Charismatics. Pastors and preachers sometimes differentiate between tithes and offerings. Some pastors teach that offerings are a part of the worship experience and are an individual choice. Other pastors teach sermon series on financial generosity and the importance of giving as part of being a follower of Jesus Christ. See Kris Vallotton's sermon on Poverty, Riches, and Wealth - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vw-QHgWJ5vo>

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics living in the United States are subject to state, federal, and local taxes. Churches that are registered through the IRS as 501c3 non-profit organizations are exempt from paying taxes.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics have access to the services of local law enforcement in their communities.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics use the Gregorian Calendar that is used worldwide.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics interact with private and government bureaucratic institutions. One example is Bethel Church's engagement with California State Legislatures to block AB2943 that was going to banning sexual orientation change efforts. Many evangelical and Neo-Charismatic leaders met with the author of the bill, Assemblymember Evan Low. Through their conversations and interactions,

Assemblymember Low withdrew consideration for the bill. See Bethel Church's statement: <https://www.bethel.com/press/cabills/>. Also see Assemblymember Low's statement: <https://a28.asmdc.org/press-release/assemblymember-low-statement-assembly-bill-2943>

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: Some churches provide formal and institutionalized poverty relief in their local communities. Many provide food, clothes, and other resources to those in need. Some of these ministries are involved in partnerships with local city and town governments in order to provide care. See City Link in Fontana, CA as an example: <https://www.wateroflifecc.org/citylinkoutreach>

Reference: Corbett, Steve, and Brian Fikkert. *When Helping Hurts*. Moody Publishers, 2014. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=BXFtSN1u-r8C>.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics have access to the judicial system through the US Constitution.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: Execution is lawfully permitted in certain states in the United States.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: Seizure of property is often done due to debt collection.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics in the United States are subject to local, state, and federal laws based upon the penal codes and constitutions.

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: Some churches provide formal and institutionalized poverty relief in their local communities. Many provide food, clothes, and other resources to those in need. Some of these ministries are involved in partnerships with local city and town governments in order to provide care. See City Link in Fontana, CA as an example: <https://www.wateroflifecc.org/citylinkoutreach>

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Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics have built their own schools that teach students the methods and doctrines of supernatural ministry. Churches such as Bethel Church founded Bethel School of Supernatural Ministry in Redding, CA. Other schools such as Wagner University have branched off from their home church (Harvest Rock in Pasadena, CA) and have become stand alone institutes that train men and women to minister out of the power of the Holy Spirit. See Wagner University at <https://wagner.university/> and Bethel School of Supernatural Ministry at <https://bssm.net/>

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics believe that there are Biblical offices and positions within the church that have greater authority than others. Many Neo-Charismatics believe that there are some leaders who are called as apostles or prophets in the modern-day. The emphasis on the role and function of apostles is not about organizational bureaucracy but rather is focused on personal leadership. Che Ahn explains, "Notice what apostolic government is shifting away from - bureaucratic authority, legal structure, control, and rational leadership. Notice what apostolic government is shifting to - personal authority,

relational structure, coordination, and charismatic leadership. For apostolic government to be effective, it must rely on the personal leadership of apostles rather than organizational systems."

Reference: Ahn, Ché. *Modern-day Apostles*. Destiny Image Publishers, 2019.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=IW2ADwAAQBAJ>.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

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Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: Tithing is a common practice amongst Neo-Charismatics. Pastors and preachers sometimes differentiate between tithes and offerings. Some pastors teach that offerings are a part of the worship experience and are an individual choice. Other pastors teach sermon series on financial generosity and the importance of giving as part of being a follower of Jesus Christ. See Kris Vallotton's sermon on Poverty, Riches, and Wealth - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vw-QHgWJ5vo>

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics living in the United States are subject to state, federal, and local taxes. Churches that are registered through the IRS as 501c3 non-profit organizations are exempt from paying taxes.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics have access to the services of local law enforcement in their communities.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

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Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

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– Yes

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↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

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Notes: Seizure of property is often done due to debt collection.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics in the United States are subject to local, state, and federal laws based upon the penal codes and constitutions.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Neo-Charismatics use the Gregorian Calendar that is used worldwide.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

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